

The Effect of Complementary Irrigation in Different Growth Stages on Yield, Qualitative and Quantitative Indices of the Two Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) Cultivars in Mazandaran

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Abstract—In most wheat growing moderate regions and especially in the north of Iran climate, is affected grain filling by several physical and abiotic stresses. In this region, grain filling often occurs when temperatures are increasing and moisture supply is decreasing. The experiment was designed in RCBD with split plot arrangements with four replications. Four irrigation treatments included (I0) no irrigation (check); (I1) one irrigation (50 mm) at heading stage; (I2) two irrigation (100 mm) at heading and anthesis stage; and (I3) three irrigation (150 mm) at heading, anthesis and early grain filling growth stage, two wheat cultivars (Milan and Shanghai) were cultured in the experiment. Totally raining was 453 mm during the growth season. The result indicated that biological yield, grain yield and harvest index were significantly affected by irrigation levels. I3 treatment produced more tillers number in m², fertile tillers number in m², harvest index and biological yield. Milan produced more tillers number in m², fertile tillers in m², while Shanghai produced heavier tillers and grain 1000 weight. Plant height was significant in wheat varieties while were not statistically significant in irrigation levels. Milan produced more grain yield, harvest index and biological yield. Grain yield shown that I1, I2, and I3 produced increasing of 5228 (21%), 5460 (27%) and 5670 (29%) kg ha⁻¹, respectively. There was an interaction of irrigation and cultivar on grain yields. In the absence of the irrigation reduced grain 1000 weight from 45 to 40 g. No irrigation reduced soil moisture extraction during the grain filling stage. Current assimilation as a source of carbon for grain filling depends on the light intercepting viable green surfaces of the plant after anthesis that due to natural senescence and the effect of various stresses. At the same time the demand by the growing grain is increasing. It is concluded from research work that wheat crop irrigated Milan cultivar could increase the grain yield in comparison with Shanghai cultivar. Although, the grain yield of Shanghai under irrigation was slightly lower than Milan. This grain yield also was related to weather condition, sowing date, plant density and location conditions and management of fertilizers, because there was not significant difference in biological and straw yield. The best result was produced by I1 treatment. I2 and I3 treatments were not significantly difference with I1 treatment. Grain yield of I1 indicated that wheat is under soil moisture deficiency. Therefore, I1 irrigation was better than I0.

Keywords—anthesis, grain yield, irrigation, supplementary, Wheat.

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I. INTRODUCTION

THE Mazandaran of North Iran is a vast, semi humid area with mean annual precipitation ranging from 600 to 900 mm. About 80% of the annual precipitation occurs from October through March. The prevailing cropping systems are continuous winter wheat systems. Continuous winter wheat systems are seeded around October and harvested around June. The severe water stress that normally occurs in this region significantly lowers yields. In this region, rain is falling mainly during the winter and a lesser amount during the warmer spring period. This rainy season is followed by a hot, dry spring.

Tahmasebi Sarvestani et al. (2004) showed that irrigation at planting plus milking stages produced the highest yield compare to irrigation at milking stage [1]. Among genotypes Sabalan genotype with average yield of 2213 kg/ha produced the highest and Sardari genotype with 1502 kg/ha had the lowest grain yield. In general supplemental irrigation caused an increment of 36 percent yield of Sabalan genotype [1].

Li et al. (2000) reported that available soil water for winter wheat was depleted gradually beginning in May and continuing until the beginning of the rainy season in late June [2]. The low precipitation period from April through June also makes it difficult to establish a good wheat stand. In years when there is sufficient available soil water at the wheat planting time or when the rains occur early in the spring season at a critical growth stage, winter wheat yield can be above mean (3 Mg ha⁻¹ for wheat) [3]. Increased production depends to a great extent on further improvement of soil water availability and efficient water use [4]. Although water deficits are unavoidable in the dry environment, studies have shown that water stress effects can be minimized by management practices that increase available soil water at planting or by supplemental irrigation [5], [6], [7]. Several studies have shown that supplemental irrigation at critical growth stages can mitigate the effects of crop water stress on yield [8], [9], [10], [11], [12]. Research in China has advanced rainwater-harvesting technologies to provide a water source for supplemental irrigation [13], [14].

Efficiency of water supplement in comparison with full water at growth period of plant is reported from 60 to 70

percent in some countries [15]. Siadat (1987) reported that means of increasing wheat and barley grain yield under supplemental irrigation are 1175 and 1088 kg/ha respectively [16]. Increasing grain wheat yield under supplemental irrigation was reported about 1 ton per hectare in Pakistan (15). Siadate (1987) reported that wheat grain yield was increased to 1748 kg/ha with using two times of supplemental irrigation at producing spike and milking stages in Kermanshah while increasing yield with irrigation in each above stage was 1500 kilogram per hectare [16].

Supplemental irrigation is defined as the application of a limited amount of water to rainfed crops when precipitation fails to provide the essential moisture for normal plant growth. This practice has shown potential in alleviating the adverse effects of unfavorable rain patterns and thus improving and stabilizing crop yields [17], [18], [19]. Early studies at ICARDA showed that applying two or three irrigations (80–200 mm) to wheat increased crop grain yield by 36 to 450%, and produced similar or even higher grain yields than in fully irrigated conditions [17]-[20]. Supplemental irrigation is widely practiced in Syria, and in southern and eastern Mediterranean countries. However, excessive use of water in supplemental irrigation because of low irrigation cost and attractive gains from increased yields has resulted in a decline of aquifers and deterioration of water quality in many areas [21]. So, the amount of rainwater that can be harvested is small relative to the area of wheat grown under water-stressed conditions. Rainfed crop production under this climate thus depends strongly on both the amount and distribution of rain. In north region, amount of rainfall is high and generally poorly distributed, so periods of water deficit occur during the grain-filling stage of wheat almost every year. The objectives of this study were (i) to evaluate how complementary irrigations can be combined to further enhance the use of limited water resources and (ii) to determine the effectiveness of complementary irrigation methods for increasing grain yield.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Experimental Site

Field experiment was conducted at the Mazandaran in farm research at Jouybar (55°11'E, 36°38'N 10 m altitude) in 2007 in the North of Iran. The site is typical lowland with the humid climate of wide seasonal variations. Precipitation distribution and totals had large differences between years. The amounts of seasonal rainfall received from planting to harvest were around 500 mm. Seventy to eighty percent of it occurs as thunderstorms during the October through April period. The greatest difference between the potential ET and precipitation occurs between May and June, and this is a critical period for winter wheat growth (Table I). The soil is loam and 0.8% soil organic matter (Table II).

B. Experimental Methods

The study was a split-plot, randomized block design with four replications. Irrigation treatments included (I0) no irrigation (check); (I1) one irrigation (50 mm) at heading

stage; (I2) two irrigation (100 mm) at heading and anthesis stage; and (I3) three irrigation (150 mm) at heading, anthesis and early grain filling growth stage. Description of Zadoks' wheat development scales; first spikelet of inflorescence (ZS=50), beginning of anthesis (ZS=60) and early milk (ZS=70). The treatments comprised two bread wheat (*T. aestivum* L.) cultivars were used (Milan and Shanghai). Wheat cultivars were the main plots and SI the subplots. The area of individual sub-plots was 8 m² (2 by 4m). Therefore, there were 32 plots. The plots were divided into 1-m strips on about 19 Nov. and the plots were broadcast-fertilized with 150 kg N ha⁻¹ as urea and 100 kg P ha⁻¹ as triple super phosphate (46% P₂O₅) and 100 kg K ha⁻¹ as sulfate potassium (46% K₂O). Nitrogen application (urea) was split; half at planting, 25% top-dressed at the early tillering stage and 25% at the Jointing. Phosphorus and potassium were applied as basal dressing. The wheat rows were planted in 15 cm rows at a seed rate of approximately 300 seeds m².

TABLE I
MEAN, MAXIMUM AND MINIMUM TEMPERATURE, RAIN AND
EVAPOTRANSPIRATION IN 2007

Variable	Nov	Des	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun
Min. tem.	12.3	4.9	1.8	4.7	4.6	9.2	14	20
Max. tem.	22.6	13	12	15	14	16	22	31
Mean tem.	16.9	8.6	8.3	9.4	8.7	13	18	26
Precipitation	91	90	119	68	59	53	17	14
Evapotrans.	63	35	25	36	51	56	94	167

TABLE II
SELECTED SOIL PROPERTIES FOR COMPOSITE SAMPLES AT EXPERIMENTAL SITE
IN 2007

Soil texture	CEC meqi	K ppm	P ppm	N %	OM %	pH	EC μ mos/cm	Depth cm
Loam	4.8	168.37	16.5	320	0.78	7.52	1.4	0-20
Loam	5.9	78.23	8.8	185	0.38	7.78	1.7	20-40

C. Measurements

Precipitation was measured daily at a weather station 3 km from the experimental field. Grain yields for experiment were determined by hand-harvesting 3 m². Grain was harvested in each plot using a combine harvest. Grain samples were air-dried on concrete, threshed, oven-dried at 70°C to a uniform moisture level, and weighed. Irrigation system was designed to ensure full and uniform water coverage and distribution. Irrigation was applied to all treatments at the same time.

D. Statistical Analysis

The data from Exp was analyzed using a split-plot, unbalanced ANOVA for data. Main plots were wheat cultivars, and subplots were irrigation in plant growth stage at irrigation. Experiment was analyzed as a randomized complete block design. The Duncan multiple range test ($P = 0.05$) was used to test the treatment means. Analyses used procedure of the SAS statistical software package [22].

III. RESULTS

The result indicated that biological yield, grain yield and harvest index were significantly affected by irrigation levels. Milan produced more grain yield, harvest index and biological yield. Grain yield shown that I1, I2, and I3 produced

increasing of 5228 (21%), 5460 (27%) and 5670 (29%) kg ha⁻¹, respectively. There was an interaction of irrigation and cultivar on grain yields. Small amounts of complementary irrigation applied to wheat significantly increased grain yield. Grain yield values varied between crop from 3825 kg/ha for nonirrigated wheat to 5963 kg/ha for plots receiving 150 mm of complementary irrigation. The greatest mean grain yield value was 5670 kg/ha when 150 mm of supplement irrigation was added at the three stage, and the lowest was 4032 kg/ha in the check.

The biological yield was greatest when complementary irrigation was applied at the three growth stage. The straw yield was mostly greater than the grain yield values. Pierre et al. (2008) show that biomass reductions under water stress tended to be higher if plots received high N fertilization [23]. When complementary irrigation was applied at heading stage, grain yield were always higher than the check, particularly when the averaged respective supplement irrigation were I0 compared with only I1. Results for yield suggested that adding

small amounts of complementary irrigation at heading can be highly effective for increased yields and that I1 can be 30% greater than the check. The first irrigation was applied around the time of heading in early April. After anthesis, grain 1000 weight under complementary irrigation was significantly greater than that under rainfed conditions. Pierre et al. (2008) show that water stress reduced grain yield and kernel weight. Grain 1000 weight was significantly influenced by complementary irrigation and cultivars, and most of the interactions [23]. Complementary irrigations significantly ($P < 0.01$) increased biological yield for grain yield but not for straw yield. The highest tiller number for grain yield was achieved at I2 in the Shanghai and I3 in the Milan. Plant height in Shanghai consistently resulted in higher biological yield but not for grain yield than plant height in Milan. This is clearly associated with the substantial increase in grain yield and biological yield with complementary irrigation. irrigation for the Milan.

TABLE III
ANALYSIS OF VARIANCE (MEAN SQUARE) OF DATA FOR PLANT HEIGHT, TILLER NUMBER, FERTILE TILLER BIOLOGICAL, STRAW AND GRAIN YIELD, GTW, HI, IN WHEAT IN VARIOUS STAGES OF GROWTH

ANOVA	D.F.	Grain yield	Biological yield	Straw yield	HI	Grain 1000 weight	Plant height	Tiller N.	Fertile tiller N.
Rep.	3								
Cul. (B)	1	**	ns	ns	*	**	**	**	**
E (a)	3								
Irr. (A)	3	**	**	**	*	**	ns	**	*
A×B	3	*	*	*	*	ns	ns	*	*
E (b)	18								
C.V. (%)	-	9.3	13.1	18.2	8	13.8	17.8	18.3	14.8

* and **: significant at the 5% and 1% levels, respectively. ns: non significant.

TABLE IV
EFFECT OF SUPPLEMENTAL IRRIGATION APPLIED AT DIFFERENT GROWTH STAGES AND CULTIVARS ON MEANS OF PLANT HEIGHT, TILLER NUMBER, FERTILE TILLER BIOLOGICAL, STRAW AND GRAIN YIELD, HARVEST INDEX, GRAIN 1000 WEIGHT ON WHEAT IN 2007

Treat.	Grain yield	Biological yield	Straw yield	HI	Grain 1000 weight	Plant height	Tiller number	Fertile tiller number
	Kg/ha	Kg/ha	Kg/ha	%	g	cm	M ²	M ²
I ₀	4032 c	9042 c	5010 c	44.5 b	40.2 c	96 a	341 c	322 c
I ₁	5228 ab	1054 ab	5315 b	49.6 a	43.8 ab	98 a	489 b	450 b
I ₂	5460 a	10975 a	5515 ab	49.7 a	44.2 ab	100 a	598 a	512 a
I ₃	5670 a	11595 a	5925 a	48.9 a	45.3 a	101 a	678 a	551 a
Mi.	5364 a	10729 a	5365 a	49.9 a	45.3 b	90 b	586 a	518 a
Sh.	4830 b	10347 a	5517 a	46.7 b	48.2 a	106 a	465 b	399 b

Within each treatment, means followed by different letter in a column are significantly different at the 0.05 probability level.

However, there were good linear relationships between grain yield and biological yield with complementary irrigation. HI for complementary irrigation ranged from 44.5 to 49.7%, depending on the complementary irrigation level and cultivar. The HI increased with increasing irrigation in the Milan and Shanghai, but there was no further increase for the I3. nonirrigation generally decreased grain yield and plant height. The highest tiller number was achieved at complementary

Tiller number, and effective tiller number significantly increased with increase in the amount of irrigation at growth stage. The average grain yield increased from 4032 to 5228 kg/ha when initial water use increased from 0 to 50 mm. The complementary irrigation applied at heading, anthesis and early grain filling growth stages resulted in a maximum grain yield. Plant height was significant in wheat varieties while were not statistically significant in irrigation levels. Plant height increased from 96 to 101 cm with an increase in the water from 0 to 150 mm. This study shows that maximum

yield of wheat is obtained when a complementary irrigation is applied at the heading stage. Milan produced more tillers number in m2, fertile tillers in m2, while Shanghai produced heavier tillers and grain 1000 weight. In the absence of the irrigation reduced grain 1000 weight from 45 to 40 g. No irrigation reduced soil moisture extraction during the grain filling stage. I3 treatment produced more tillers number in m2, fertile tillers number in m2, harvest index and biological yield. So, the best result was produced by I1 treatment. I2 and I3 irrigation were not significantly difference with I1 treatment. Grain yield of I1 indicated that wheat is under soil moisture deficiency. Therefore, I1 irrigation was better than I0.

IV. DISCUSSION

In the rainfed farming systems of the Mazandaran region, where water supply is often limited due to high rain, agronomic practices should aim to utilize the water available

for crop growth in an efficient way. Improved production from a limited water supply can result from increasing the total amount of water used by the crop through complementary irrigation, and improving the efficiency of water use through the adoption of deficit irrigation. Supplemental irrigation at or after anthesis not only allows the plant to increase its photosynthesis rate [24] but, more importantly, gives the plant extra time in which to translocate carbohydrate reserves to the grain [25]. These values are comparable to those found under greenhouse conditions [26] and under field conditions in South Australia [27].

The increase in water use efficiency under supplemental irrigation is associated with the increased leaf area and its effect on the ratio of soil evaporation to crop transpiration [25] and increased root growth and its effect on water extraction [28]. This work shows that the common practice of complementary irrigation, which aims at satisfying full irrigation requirements, is not the most efficient in water use for the Mazandaran rainfed environment. Applying I1 of the complementary irrigation requirements, during and after anthesis, substantially improve irrigation water productivity. The loss in yield due to deficit irrigation is small compared with the savings in irrigation water. If this is combined with an early sowing and adequate N application, a high yield may be achieved and, in addition, up to 25% of the grain yield can be increased for expansion of the area irrigated. Angus and Herwaarden (2001) show that difference between the efficiencies for the total dry matter and grain was due to an accumulation of cellulose in the stems during grain filling [29]. Finally, current assimilation as a source of carbon for grain filling depends on the light intercepting viable green surfaces of the plant after anthesis that due to natural senescence and the effect of various stresses. At the same time the demand by the growing grain is increasing.

V. CONCLUSION

Wheat grown in the semi humid area of Iran often suffers seasonal water stress that results in lower grain yields. Complementary irrigation had a significant effect on grain yield of winter wheat grown in soil particularly when small amounts of water are added at critical growth stage. In this study, portion of grain yield from biological yield were greater than straw yield and about 50% or greater for the complementary irrigation winter wheat. The use of complementary irrigation was highly effective in increasing grain yield. Complementary irrigation using a small amount of water at a critical time is an efficient practice to mitigate water stress and increase yields. However, available water for irrigation is not limited in humid areas, and practices for increasing yield at time of seeding are highly desirable. However, this study showed that complementary irrigation greatly increased the amount of water used by the wheat and resulted in increased grain yields. In the regions, complementary irrigation at heading was more important for winter wheat than for check because relatively high amounts of rainfall normally occur during the wheat growing season in contrast to the usually dry conditions for the latter portion of

the wheat growing season. The study clearly showed that using I1 much of the soil can greatly enhance soil water storage and increase wheat yield. Thus, intensive farming technologies for grain increase are adopted and practiced. Although the complementary irrigation for grain crops is a labor and capital intensive technology, it was developed and is being applied due to significant yield increases. Angus and Herwaarden (2001) [29] show that alternative of conserving water for ET after anthesis is a more promising means of increasing yield, despite a lower TE, because transpiration leads directly to an increase grain growth, as [24] showed.

Thus, it is concluded from research work that wheat crop irrigated Milan cultivar could increase the grain yield in comparison with Shanghai cultivar. Although, the grain yield of Shanghai under irrigation was slightly lower than Milan. This grain yield also was related to weather condition, sowing date, plant density and location conditions and management of fertilizers, because there was not significant difference in biological and straw yield.

REFERENCES

- [1] Z. Tahmasebi Sarvestani, S. A. M. Modarres Sanavy, and A. Roohi, "Yield and yield components of dryland wheat genotypes under supplemental irrigation," Proceedings of the 4th International Crop Science Congress Brisbane, Australia, 2004.
- [2] F. R. Li, S. Cook, G. T. Geballe, and W. R. Burch, "Rainwater harvesting agriculture: An integrated system for water management on rainfed land in China's semiarid areas," *Ambio*, Vol. 29, pp.477-483, 2000.
- [3] F. M. Li, Q. H. Song, H. S. Liu, F. R. Li, and X. L. Liu, "Effects of pre-plant irrigation and phosphate application on water use and yield of spring wheat under semi-arid conditions," *Agric. Water Manage.*, Vol. 45, pp. 32-48, 2001.
- [4] X. Y. Li, J. D. Gong, and Q. Z. Gao, "Rainfall harvesting and sustainable agriculture development in the Loess Plateau of China," *J. Desert Res.*, Vol. 20, pp. 150-153, 1999.
- [5] J. T. Musick, and D. A. Dusek, "Irrigated corn yield response to water," *Trans. ASAE*, Vol. 23, pp. 92-98, 1980.
- [6] R. K. Misra, and T. N. Chaudhary, "Effect of limited water input on root growth, water use, and grain yield of wheat," *Field Crops Res.*, Vol. 10, pp. 125-134, 1985.
- [7] F. M. Rhoads, and R. L. Stanley, "Response of three corn hybrids to low levels of soil moisture tension in the plow layer," *Agron. J.*, Vol. 65, pp. 315-318, 1973.
- [8] P. Fox, and J. Rockstrom, "Supplemental irrigation for dry-spell mitigation of rainfed agriculture in the Sahel. *Agric.*" *Water Manage.*, Vol. 61, pp. 29-50, 2003.
- [9] P. R. Gajri, and S. S. Prihar, "Effect of small irrigation amounts on the yield of wheat," *Agric. Water Manage.*, Vol. 6, pp. 31-41, 1983.
- [10] R. A. Fisher, "The effects of water stress at various stages of development on yield process in wheat," pp. 169-174. *In* Plant response to climatic factors. Proc. Symp., Uppsala, Sweden, 15-20 Sept. 1970. UNESCO, Paris, 1970.
- [11] A. D. Schneider, J. T. Musick, and D. A. Dusek, "Efficient wheat irrigation with limited water," *Trans. ASAE*, Vol. 12, pp. 23-26, 1969.
- [12] N. T. Singh, R. Singh, P. S. Mahajan, and A. C. Vig, "Influence of supplement irrigation and presowing soil water storage on wheat," *Agron. J.*, Vol. 71, pp. 483-486, 1979
- [13] X. Y. Li, and J. D. Gong, "Effects of different ridge: furrow ratios and supplemental irrigation on crop production in ridge and furrow rainfall harvesting system with mulches," *Agric. Water Manage.*, Vol. 54, pp. 243-254, 2002.
- [14] Z. P. Shangguan, M. A. Shao, T. W. Lei, and T.L. Fan, "Runoff water management technologies for dryland agriculture on the Loess Plateau of China," *Int. J. Sustainable Dev. World Ecol.*, Vol. 9, pp. 341-350, 2002.

- [15] E. R. Perrier, and A. B. Salkini, "Supplemental irrigation in the Near East and North Africa. Kluwer Academic publisher," Boston/London, 1987.
- [16] H. Siadat, "Supplemental irrigation systems in Iran," pp. 327-364. In: E. R. perrier and A. B. Salkini, supplemental irrigation in the near east north Africa, Kluwer Academic publisher, Boston, London, 1987.
- [17] E. R. Perrier, and A. B. Salkini, "Supplemental irrigation in the Near East and North Africa," Netherlands: Kluwer Acad. Publ, 1991.
- [18] T. Oweis, M. Pala, and J. Ryan, "Stabilizing rainfed wheat yields with supplemental irrigation in a Mediterranean-type climate," *Agron. J.*, Vol. 90, pp.672-681, 1998
- [19] H. Zhang, and T. Oweis, "Water-yield relations and optimal irrigation scheduling of wheat in the Mediterranean region," *Agric. Water Manage.*, Vol. 38, pp. 195-211, 1999.
- [20] T. Oweis, "Supplemental irrigation: An option for improved water use efficiency," pp. 115-131. *In Proc. Regional Seminar on the Optimization of Irrigation in Agriculture*, Amman, Jordan, pp. 21-24. 1994.
- [21] K. Ward, and P. Smith, "An investigation into the shallow groundwater resources of part of Northwest Syria," pp. 29-42. *In Annual Report of Farm Resource Management Program*, ICARDA, Aleppo, Syria, 1994.
- [22] SAS Institute, "SAS user's guide: Statistics," SAS Inst., Cary, NC, 1991.
- [23] C. S. Pierre, C. J. Peterson, A. S. Ross, J. B. Ohm, M. C. Verhoeven, M. Larson, and B. Hoefler, "White wheat grain quality changes with genotype, nitrogen fertilization, and water stress," *Agronomy Journal*, Vol. 100, pp. 414-420, 2008.
- [24] J. B. Passioura, "Physiology of grain yield in wheat growing on stored water," *J. Aust. Inst. Agric. Sci.*, Vol. 3, pp. 117-120, 1976.
- [25] H. Zhang, T. Oweis, S. Garabet, and M. Pala, "Water use efficiency and transpiration efficiency of wheat under rainfed and irrigation conditions in a Mediterranean environment," *Plant Soil*, Vol. 201, pp. 295-305, 1998.
- [26] J. B. Passioura, "Roots and drought resistance," *Agric. Water Manage.*, Vol. 7, pp. 265-280, 1983.
- [27] R. J. French, and T. E. Schultz, "Water use efficiency of wheat in a Mediterranean-type environment: I. The relation between yield, water use and climate," *Aust. J. Agric. Res.*, Vol. 35, pp. 743-764, 1984.
- [28] P. J. M. Cooper, P. J. Gregory, D. Tully, and H. C. Harris, "Improving water use efficiency of annual crops in the rainfed farming systems of West Asia and North Africa." *Exp. Agric.*, Vol. 23, pp. 113-158, 1987.
- [29] J. F. Angus, and A.F. Herwaarden, "Increasing water use and water use efficiency in dryland wheat," *Agronomy Journal*, Vol. 93, pp. 290-298, 2001.